

Yield potential

Morphophysiological parameters of three irrigated rice varieties

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We evaluated the morphophysiological parameters for differentiating the productivity potential of irrigated rice varieties EEA406 (traditional type), Bluebelle (intermediate type), and BR-IRGA409 (semidwarf type) through quantitative analysis of plant growth.

We evaluated plant growth during the cropping cycle by measuring dry matter and total leaf area at seven growth stages (see figure). We determined the parameters of crop growth rate (CGR), relative growth rate (RGR), net assimilation rate (NAR), and leaf area index (LAI) using modern or functional methodology. Conversion of solar energy to biomass (Ec) was calculated as

Sampling

EEA 406 — 1 — 2 — 3 — 4 — 5 — 6 — 7
Bluebelle — 1 — 2 — 3 — 4 — 5 — 6 — 7
BR-IRGA409 — 1 — 2 — 3 — 4 — 5 — 6 — 7

Crop growth rate and conversion of solar energy to Biomass for 3 irrigated rice varieties during 7 growth stages, Brazil.

$100 \times (\text{CGR} \times 3.7) / (\text{RS} \times 0.45)$
where RS is the incident solar energy, 3.7 is the energy (kcal) per gram of dry matter, and 0.45 is the fraction of RS used in photosynthesis.

The CGR and Ec were the morphophysiological parameters that permitted the differentiation of the three varieties.

Grain quality

A method to synthesize the aroma of certain varieties of fragrant Indian rice

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Only one fragrance component, 2-acetyl-1-pyrroline (AP), of boiled Basmati rice has been identified. We have noticed that an aroma completely different from AP is produced at a lower temperature. It closely resembles the sweet odor of four varieties of indigenous unboiled rice. This aroma molecule has the same R_f value as do unboiled rice of those strains but it is very different from that of AP.

Results were variable when we tried to produce the aroma using a mechanical mixture of proline, silica, and sucrose heated at a lower temperature. We instead tried aqueous solutions of sucrose and proline in a new series of experiments. Results were best when 1.1 g proline and

BR-IRGA409 showed higher CGR than the other varieties; Bluebelle showed less. After the flag leaf appeared, BR-IRGA409 was the most efficient in Ec, followed by EEA406 and then Bluebelle. This explained the greater observed yield, which had the same rank order as CGR and Ec. □

3.4 g sucrose were dissolved in 6 ml water into which 3 g silica was then mixed. This formed a paste that was heated to 128-135°C. Within 15-20 min, an aroma of good quality rice was produced. A solution of proline or sucrose alone yields no such aroma.

Good aroma was also produced using 1.5 g proline, 1 g fructose, 3 ml water, and 2.5 g silica heated to the same temperature range. The reaction temperature is sharply defined; no aroma is produced at 124°C. The rate of AP synthesis is poor, as is the yield of aroma.

By fitting a bent tube to the reaction vessel, an alkaline aqueous fluid can be collected. When trapped in acid-water and thus rendered alkaline, it produces a different odor that is later converted into a rice aroma.

After collecting a sufficient amount of the aroma, gas chromatograph-mass spectrometer analysis can be performed to establish the formula of this new component. □

Pest resistance—diseases

Characteristics of some rice varieties resistant to *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav.

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We evaluated 25 blast-resistant rice varieties from seven regions in China to determine resistance characteristics. Three susceptible varieties served as controls.

Seeds were sown in plastic pots that

were filled with soil. We selected uniform rice seedlings and inoculated them 3 wk after sowing with 50 monoconidial isolates of *P. oryzae* from 20 races. Spore suspension was sprayed at a concentration of $1-2 \times 10^5$ conidia/ml. Inoculated plants were incubated in a dew chamber for 24 h at 25°C and then kept in a humid room with an automatic mister for 1 wk at 24-28°C before we assessed the disease using the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Seedlings inoculated with isolate ZB₁ (85-14) were used to assess relative

Table 1. Type, origin, and R+M% of rice varieties tested for blast resistance.

Type and variety	Region	Races (no.) producing given reaction ^a					R+M (%) ^b (0-4)
		HR 0	R 1-2	M 3-4	S 5-7	HS 8-9	
Japonica							
Dangen 1	Liaoying	49	1	0	0	0	100
Chente 232	Zhejiang	45	0	2	3	0	94
A36 line 16	Jiling	45	2	0	3	0	94
Dushouxi 1	Jiling	39	2	5	4	0	92
1344	Jiling	38	6	2	3	1	92
Jiangxinu	Jiangsu	41	2	3	4	0	92
Ji 86A-48	Jiling	37	3	6	5	0	90
C102	Liaoying	43	2	0	4	1	90
Jiahu 5	Zhejiang	42	0	3	4	1	90
Guizaoshen	Jiling	34	5	4	7	0	86
Nonghu 6 (check)	Zhejiang	4	2	4	35	5	20
Indica							
Xiangya 1	Jiangsu	47	1	1	1	0	98
Suweon 290	Korea	47	1	1	1	0	98
Shuanzao 25	Guangdong	44	1	4	1	0	98
528-4	Hunan	47	0	1	1	1	96
Zhi 20-5	Guangdong	46	1	1	1	1	96
81005	Guangdong	44	1	2	3	0	91
Ming 119	Fujian	37	3	5	4	1	90
Mingnu 706	Fujian	37	5	3	5	0	90
Zhuke 2	Zhejiang	38	2	5	4	1	90
Jiannongzao 9	Fujian	39	3	2	5	1	88
Xiangzhou 5	Hunan	36	1	7	6	1	86
Zhe 852	Zhejiang	38	3	1	8	0	84
Sanyangai 1	Guangdong	33	2	7	8	1	82
Erjiufeng	Zhejiang	37	1	3	8	1	82
Zhefu 802	Zhejiang	36	2	2	6	4	80
Guangluai 4 (check)	Zhejiang	16	4	4	20	6	48
Yuanfengzao (check)	Zhejiang	9	1	2	31	7	24

^aHR = highly resistant (SES blast score 0), R = resistant (1-2), M = moderate (3-4), S = susceptible (5-7), HS = highly susceptible (8-9). ^bR+M% = percent with SES scores 0-4.

Table 2. Some components of resistance to *P. oryzae* strain ZB₁ (85-14) in rice varieties.

Variety	Relative infection efficiency		Lesion size (mm ²)	Difference in infectivity (%)
	Total lesions/ plant (no.)	Sporulating lesions/plant (no.)		
1344	3.00	1.33	0.46	18.8
C102	3.00	2.00	0.84	12.5
Ji 86A-48	6.60	2.25	0.43	15.5
Dushouxi 1	4.22	2.33	0.40	56.3
Guizaoshen	3.89	2.00	0.74	75.0
Jiangxinu	5.86	3.67	0.65	31.8
Nonghu 6 (check)	18.93	15.50	3.55	100.0
Mingnu 706	1.33	1.33	0.48	15.8
Jiannongzao 9	1.75	1.00	0.39	21.1
Shuanzao 25	1.50	1.17	0.61	40.0
Zhefu 802	2.67	2.00	0.64	17.6
Xiangzhou 5	4.00	2.00	0.80	50.0
Ming 119	3.20	1.50	0.57	26.3
Sanyangai 1	3.50	2.13	0.59	60.0
Erjiufeng	5.00	4.00	2.30	33.3
81005	6.50	3.33	1.39	22.2
Zhuke 2	13.00	10.17	2.37	100.0
Guangluai 4 (check)	7.47	5.71	3.70	96.2
Yuanfengzao (check)	11.44	7.67	3.62	100.0

infection efficiency (RIE, based on lesions per plant), lesion size (LS), and difference in infectivity ([DIE], the percentage of infected plants 7 d after inoculation).

The 25 varieties showed a broad spectrum of resistance, with R+M% >80% for the 50 isolates tested (Table 1).

Studies on some components of partial resistance to the isolate ZB₁ (85-14) found that this isolate did not infect nine varieties, thus showing vertical resistance to the isolate. The 16 other varieties were infected by the isolate, but had less RIE, smaller LS, and lower DIE than the susceptible varieties, indicating partial resistance to the isolate (Table 2). □

Inducing rice blast (BI) resistance by inoculating with an incompatible race of *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav.

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We studied the ability of an incompatible BI race to induce resistance to a compatible race in the greenhouse using rice variety Zhenlong 13.

We mixed the incompatible and compatible races and inoculated the plant at the 4-leaf stage. Inoculation density of the compatible race was 10⁵ conidia/ml; that of the incompatible race varied (Table 1).

In a second experiment, plants were inoculated first with the incompatible race, followed by the compatible race 1, 2, and 3 d later. Disease intensity was assessed 7 d after inoculation.

The experiments were repeated twice with three replications each.

The incompatible race induced resistance to the compatible race only when it was introduced before or simultaneously with the compatible race (Table 2). □